

Robotic Guide Dog Using Parallel Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—This abstract presents a massively parallel deep reinforcement learning approach designed to interpret human behavior within a quadruped robot system functioning as a guide dog for visually impaired individuals. The system includes a supervisory module integrated with a control scheme that ensures safe interaction between the human and the quadruped robot. It effectively distinguishes between different human actions, such as stopping, turning, and walking. The trained network builds upon another network capable of robustly managing quadruped locomotion over challenging terrains. The efficacy of this approach is evaluated within a simulation environment based on a physics engine.

Index Terms—Legged robotics, Reinforcement learning, Assistive robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to autonomously traverse the environment is crucial for people, and this task is particularly challenging for visually impaired people. Currently, guide dogs are the best option in terms of safety and responsiveness, while also providing companionship. However, the demand for guide dogs significantly exceeds the supply, while the training of a single dog taking up to 2 years and costing between \$40-50K [1]. Considering these factors, quadruped robots present a viable alternative from a supply, time, and cost perspective, though they cannot fully replace the companionship offered by real dogs.

For both guide dogs and robotic alternatives, it is essential to not only guide the human but also interpret various commands delivered through a leash or harness [2], [3]. This abstract presents a preliminary study on a learning-based approach to model and interpret user commands through a leash for a robotic guide dog system. This work is an excerpt from [4].

II. METHODOLOGY

The approach adopts a modular structure, separating locomotion and interpretation into distinct neural networks. A low-level neural network manages the locomotion control, while a high-level (or supervisory) neural network interprets the forces

The research leading to these results has been supported by the COW-BOT project, in the frame of the PRIN 2020 research program, grant n. 2020NH7EAZ_002, the ARIEL project, in the frame of the PRIN 2022 research program, grant n. 2022WS29WP, funded by the European Union Next-Generation EU, and the DARC project, in the frame of the PRIN 2022 PNRR research program, grant n. P2022MHR5C, funded by the European Union Next-Generation EU. The authors are solely responsible for its content.

Fig. 1: (a) The proposed robotic guide dog system. (b) The training environment (4096 parallel simulated robots).

imparted on a rigid leash, placed on the back of the ANYmal D quadruped robot (Fig. 1a), and translate them into velocity commands for the low-level control. This modularity (Fig. 2) also allows for the integration of different low-level control schemes without the need to re-train of the supervisor network, as long as the commands remain consistent.

By leveraging the Isaac Lab framework [5], both the locomotion and the supervisory network were developed via massively parallel deep reinforcement learning (MPDRL) [6]. This approach takes advantage of the PPO learning algorithm [7], which trains on data sampled from parallel environments. This enhances time efficiency and produces a controller that is robust to variations in physical parameters via domain randomisation: therefore, we successfully simulated 4096 robotic guide dogs (Fig. 1b).

III. SUPERVISOR POLICY

As this is a preliminary study, the human behaviour has been simplified and synthesised into four possible commands.

- *Stop*. A pulling force towards the user of 40 N or above should be interpreted as a stopping command
- *Move straight*. A pulling force towards the user of less than 40 N is not considered an explicit command, and should be interpreted as a 'keep going' command.
- *Steer*. A lateral force of 20 N or higher should be interpreted as a steering command, so the robot should steer proportionally to the force.
- *Stop and turn*. Applying both a lateral force over 20 N and a pulling force over 40 N should be interpreted as a "turn in place" command.

Fig. 2: The proposed control scheme design.

Fig. 3: (a) Comparison between the baseline locomotion training with lower disturbances and the proposed environment with force disturbances from the human user. (b) The evolution of the sum of the behavioural rewards, where on average 1 is the optimal value based on the reward weights.

The threshold for the pulling force was determined based on [1], while the lateral force threshold was heuristically set to half of the pulling force. The supervisor network operates independently of these thresholds, which are instead integrated into the reward function. During evaluation, forces in each environment are compared to the thresholds, and the reward function for the identified behaviour is calculated by comparing the velocity command output to the desired one. In addition to these primary rewards, there are also shaping rewards, such as action rate and velocity limits.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed supervisor network is trained in a physics-based-simulator, leveraging a pre-trained low-level locomotion control network, over 3000 iterations. The network is then tested under various pulling and lateral force conditions to evaluate both the robot’s resilience to external inputs and its ability to accurately interpret the received force signals, and its results are shown in 4. The data analysis shows highly satisfactory results, as well as some limit case problems. The robot achieved a mean episode duration equivalent to the locomotion baseline (Fig. 3a), indicating that it adapts to the transmitted forces without falling. Furthermore, it correctly responds to different force inputs, successfully learning the desired behaviour from the rewards (Fig. 3b).

V. FUTURE PROSPECTS

The proposed approach yielded promising results in interpreting the intended behaviours, though these represent

Fig. 4: The success rate on different applied forces. In blue forces in the explored space, in yellow on thresholds and boundaries, in red outside the explored space.

a simplified version of potential human interactions. Future work will extend this preliminary analysis by applying such learning approach to more realistic human behaviours, which are generally more complex and harder to synthesize than those considered in this study.

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